

INCLUSIVE-ENOUGH STUDENT ENGAGEMENT: A TRANSNATIONAL DEMOCRATIC GOVERNANCE MODEL FOR STUDENT PARTICIPATION IN EUROPEAN UNIVERSITIES

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Target	Any European University Alliance, any University in the European Union, Quality Assurance Agencies in the EHEA, European Commission (DG EAC), HEI Sector

The objective of this Good Practice is twofold:

- to generate top-down evidence that demonstrates the importance of inclusive governance models that incorporate democratically elected student representatives across any Higher Education Institution operating within EHEA
- to provide a bottom-up practical guide that enables any HEI to adapt this practice, outlining the processes required to develop the core characteristics of a democratic system for the inclusion of student representatives in institutional governance.

Accordingly, the Good Practice pursues two main outcomes:

- to identify key implementation elements for the development of governance systems that are more effective, participatory, distributed, and representative of the communities they serve;
- to offer structured guidance for the design of such systems, while fostering institutional creativity through an adaptable and flexible model that encourages the development of innovative and context-sensitive democratic methodologies.

Its values are grounded in:

- the fundamental role it can play within the pathway outlined by the EU towards democratic, inclusive, empowering, and responsibility-oriented development of our communities;
- the organisational, economic, and social investment it represents for European Higher Education Institutions.

This Good Practice addresses the deficit in student engagement and provides a model that produces tangible value for all the members of Higher Education institutions that choose to implement it.

THE STRATEGIC CONTEXT

Student Engagement through representation models is fundamental for the success of European Higher Education Institutions

In contemporary Higher Education, students' active engagement in governance has been widely recognized as a critical factor for effective institutional functioning.⁽¹⁾

While student participation is often encouraged, its formalization through structured representative bodies remains uneven.⁽²⁾

Across Europe, concrete models vary by country and institution, creating a lack of relevance for representatives and poor outcomes in most settings.

Roles range from full voting members in core governing bodies (more common in corporatist systems) to advisory members focused on quality assurance and "student experience".⁽³⁾

These systems fall along a spectrum from corporatist, legally entrenched models to pluralist, market-oriented arrangements, with an overall trend toward stronger "student voice" but often weaker formal decision-making power.⁽⁴⁾

Various scholars have argued that higher education is being 'reverse engineered' and becoming increasingly influenced across Europe, by a processes of marketisation.^(5–12)

The trend in institutional governance across Europe can clearly be seen as weakening formal student participation and strengthening informal student participation. ⁽¹³⁾

While both student representation and student partnership are a means of realising the aspiration of student voice in higher education, they differ and the difference matters.⁽¹⁴⁾

Positioning student partners risks diminishing the importance of elected student representation systems in favour of staff selected student partner models, which can lead to tremendous consequences for individual academic and professional performances, institutional effectiveness and overall civic education of our communities. ⁽¹⁴⁾

These outcomes vary extensively, greatly influenced by even minimal variation in the applied processes as it pertains student engagement.^(15–17)

By blurring and conflating student representation and student partnership, students mandate, relevance, accountability and legitimacy, are disregarded to the detriment of student voice more broadly in higher education.⁽¹⁴⁾

This signals an effective devaluation of the participation of students, making them a minority group in the most important institutional structures.

Therefore, the students' ability to propose agendas more in line with their own interests, to assert their points of view, as well as their impact on decisions, are compromised.

If, in addition to this, we consider the knowledge and appropriate preparation that students need to successfully carry out this type of task, the ability to participate in these important forums is significantly lower as compared to the power and influence that others hold in the hierarchy of actors.^(4,18)

Some scholars outline how student partnership approaches, if promoted instead of student representation, are an illusion of the student voice that indirectly leads only to the perception of inclusion, while creating risks of patronage, tokenism, and ageism and concentrating decision-making elsewhere.(12)

As a result, many Universities and Institutions lack student engagement and find difficulties in implementing proper and effective student participation in governance processes.(18)

It's important then, to differentiate student representative structures by outlining the dangers informality poses when denying students structural power in unavoidable education micropolitics.

Reframing the student representation and partnership in terms of politics and power is crucial to understand the issues caused by relying on appointed students as opposed to elected ones.(2)

Undeniable differences between the two approaches in regard to political mechanisms and proportions of power, suggests that the student partnership approach can jeopardize civic education and social engagement in the future.

Basic fundamental characteristics for an efficient, inclusive and democratic selection of the Student Representatives engaged in decision making processes are necessary to develop coherent and virtuous values, skills, knowledge and attitudes.(19)

Through effective and inclusive student representation based on democratic safeguards that allow for a larger number and a wider array of students participating in consultations and activities, this microcosmic civil society extension can lead to the beneficial aspects of the student partnerships approach while avoiding or reducing the issues that a student partnership approach reaches.(2)

By recognising the important differences between student representation and student partnership, these two valuable roles can work together across any decisional level, shaping educational life for students.(14)

A robust student-engagement model combines both, primarily by ensuring that elected representatives retain formal authority, then investing in diverse students engagement as partners in everyday projects to enhance educational design and quality.(2)

Moreover, a culture of student voice is more likely to be realised when students have proof that they can actively participate in decision making processes related to their everyday educational and communitarian experiences: elected student representatives must be taken seriously in formalised governance structures of the institution, to obtain a strong engagement and fruitful outcomes.(14)

Nonetheless, this Good Practice is grounded on the proof that the value of education cannot be measured only in individual knowledge and skills, but in any person's capacity to build effective and productive activities in various socially significant situations.(20)

As stated by the European Commission: “Participation and active citizenship is about having the right, the means, the space and the opportunity and where necessary the support to participate in and influence decisions and engage in actions and activities so as to contribute to building a better society.”⁽²¹⁾

The aim of this Good Practice is to share the framework applied in the UNITA Alliance, to build a fully working Student Assembly based on broad, inclusive, democratic elections inside the Alliance community.

It wants to address the lack of student participation in decision-making processes and the lack of effective student involvement, fostering student empowerment and enabling them to grow in civic and social education—all while legitimizing their presence within university institutions.

UNITA would like to show how student representatives’ full inclusion in decision making processes at all levels of the Alliance, through democratic electoral processes, is key for the development of the Higher Education Sector and their members.

The process applied in the UNITA Alliance positions students as active partners in ensuring preparedness, relevance, trust and innovation within higher education institutions.

It is designed to be self-sustaining, based on the most relevant European values and democratic governance principles and is the first step for real student engagement, acknowledgement, accountability and civic education.

The whole process has been developed, coordinated and produced by the students of the UNITA Alliance.

Student Engagement through representation models is fundamental for civic and social development in the European Union

The European University Alliances Initiative (EUAs) is not only an internationalisation programme, but also a strategic action of the European Union based on the necessity to build a stronger Community, that recognizes Universities as a fundamental starting point.

The university is a cornerstone of our societies. It holds, and must defend, its primacy as the centre of knowledge. It is the guarantor of freedom of expression, constructive dialogue, and transformative capacity. It is the primary driver of innovation, inclusion, and change rooted in critical thinking.

Universities bear the demanding responsibility to educate:

- citizens before workers,
- human beings who are conscious and autonomous in their thinking before competent professionals,
- communities capable of adapting to change while preserving identity and the capacity to act.

Only if universities are able to fulfill all these roles, the European Community will be able to secure a prosperous future in a reality that is constantly evolving and highly-demanding, such as the one we are living in today.

Students are arguably the primary beneficiaries of EUAs' cross-border initiatives aimed at enriching personal and professional development. Yet their systematic inclusion in EUA governance remains under-developed.(22)

Within this context, student representation constitutes a “social laboratory” of inestimable value for society as a whole.(23–27)

The inclusion of student representatives in decision-making processes is an essential component in the development of future leaders and of a European Community that is aware, critical, and actively engaged.

Moreover, as found in many scientific papers, Universities that succeed in including student representatives in decision making processes obtains:(23–35)

- Improved Learning Experiences, shaped better thanks to efficient feedback-loops
- Increased perception of Institutional Value and a stronger sense of belonging by the members of the community, that promote higher levels of student satisfaction.
- Improvements in Quality Assurance results
- Better resource allocation thanks to a larger set of innovative solutions
- Better outcomes in policy processes, thanks to the legitimization that student associations involvement grants

These results can be obtained solely through the necessary educational progress of all student representatives, whereby those will develop a larger set of skills and obtain networking opportunities with Professional and Mentors, having the chance to manage real life problems in complex contexts.

Student Engagement through representation models must be based on democratic means and processes

Within Alliances and Universities, distributed, inclusive, representative, and democratically elected governance takes on a strategic importance that goes far beyond organisational investment: it fulfills, first and foremost, an educational and social function.⁽²⁴⁾

It provides all the theoretical and practical tools necessary to understand, accept, and navigate the checks and balances, the equilibria, and the compromises that characterise truly inclusive groups.

It fosters a sense of agency, preparing students for active citizenship and future leadership roles.

This is particularly relevant considering that it addresses individuals who have reached legal adulthood, who should already be capable of managing their social responsibilities.

Universities count thousands if not tens and hundreds of thousands of students.

European University Alliances have an average of 170.000 students at the present time.⁽³⁶⁾

Communities of this size must provide systematic processes to ensure representativeness, as democratic stakeholder participation is underlined as fundamental to ensure responsiveness, transparency, and equity. ^(37–57)

As already highlighted in the first part of this introduction: inclusive institutions, characterised by broad participation, political competition, and balances of power, are those that offer the strongest prospects for development, innovation, and sustainable long-term growth.⁽⁵⁸⁾

Voting ensures electoral legitimacy, while at the same time conferring full accountability with regard to the new responsibilities associated with the role undertaken.

This assumption of responsibility is the key to the significant potential that resides in the development of a democratically elected student representation: it enables students to become the primary advocates of university activities, as actors who have contributed to the decision-making processes, have examined and understood the decisions taken, have made them their own, and have assumed responsibility for their outcomes.

Accountability is essential to ensure that governments are responsive, efficient, transparent and equitable in their decision-making processes. It also signals institutional openness, transparency, and responsiveness to stakeholder needs, which can improve trust and cooperation between students and university leadership.^(37–53,53,59,60)

When student representatives are elected through a transparent and competitive democratic process:

- Students candidated as representatives are the first to be informed and to seek to inform their community about how the institution operates, its initiatives, its progress, and the future that the community can envision.
- Students elected as representatives assume responsibility for the outcomes of the decisions in which they have taken part in. They are the first to strive to foster a strong sense of belonging to the institution, by informing and engaging the student community in the reflections undertaken, the decisions made, and the actions carried out.

Within universities, during constructive exchanges on matters of governance and of strategic direction, the academic faculty and staff members instinctively reaffirm their educational role and guide students in the debate, thereby contributing to their intellectual and civic development.(61–71)

Putting the concepts learned into practice is the most effective way to ensure that those concepts become embedded in learners' activities.(72)

Multiple studies show that participation in student governance is strongly positively associated with increased civic engagement in adulthood, including higher rates of voting, community service, and organizational involvement. These effects are observed across diverse contexts and persist several years after graduation. In fact, graduates with governance experience often report greater leadership efficacy and motivation, and are more likely to assume leadership positions in their communities and workplaces. (14,23,25,27,33,68,73)

Moreover, this practice enables a further step forward in the transnational integration of decision-making processes: it embodies the democratic values of the European project and fosters closer collaboration and cultural exchange between students and staff from the Member States.

Alignment with the EU Strategy and Reference Framework

The practice is fully aligned with the strategic pillars of the European Union for Higher Education.

The EU calls for supporting universities as “beacons of our European way of life”, by promoting democratic practices, the EU’s fundamental values, and academic freedom.⁽⁷⁴⁾ The Directorate-General for Education has underlined that the transformational potential of the European Universities initiative is rooted in its ability “to bring Europeans closer together and nurture understanding”.⁽⁷⁵⁾

The proposed method is aligned with the European Strategy for Universities (ES4U), as it seeks to address the lack of incentives for student engagement and the limited plurality in student participation, by strengthening the accountability of these fundamental members of the academic community and of the institutions themselves.⁽⁷⁶⁾

The European Education Area (EEA) aims to foster a Union characterised by democracy, solidarity and inclusion, in which education must “help empower young people to express themselves and to engage, to participate and to shape the future.”⁽⁷⁶⁾

The EEA was established on the understanding that “education is the foundation for personal fulfilment, employability and active, responsible citizenship. It is essential to the vitality of European societies and economies.”⁽⁷⁷⁾

Furthermore, the EEA consistently grounds its work in the principles of the European Pillar of Social Rights, which includes the right to quality and inclusive education as a prerequisite for full participation in society.⁽⁷⁸⁾

The organisation of the governing body proposed in this Good Practice reflects the requirements of the Standards and Guidelines for Quality Assurance in the European Higher Education Area (ESG), in particular the standard requiring the involvement of internal stakeholders in quality assurance processes.⁽⁷⁹⁾

This approach is also consistent with the conclusions on the European Universities initiative “Bridging higher education, research, innovation and society”, which set out a vision of inter-university European campuses, seamless mobility, and the integration of education, research, and the third mission.⁽⁷⁶⁾

Through the analysis of the European publications on the matters, the Alliances have required standards, such as: ^(76,79,79,80)

- the co-creation of policies
- Multilevel participation
- Transparency and accountability
- Inclusiveness and equal opportunities

Therefore: ^(76,79,79,80)

- Students must be included in strategic decision-making processes

- Students participation has to span from the quality of teaching to any detail of the overall governance of the educational facilities and their services
- Students must have access to reasoned, understandable and verifiable decisions
- Governance must be open to all students, not just selected or appointed groups.

This Good Practice achieves the three main objectives of the EU Youth Strategy (2019–2027): to engage, connect, and empower young people.⁽⁸¹⁾

It aligns with the European Skills Agenda and satisfies the competences required by 1 of the 5 “basic skills” defined in the Union of Skills: “The ability to act responsibly and participate fully in civic life, grounded in an understanding of social, economic, legal and political structures. This involves understanding and evaluation of civic and democratic concepts, institutions and processes, including democracy, media literacy, crisis preparedness and respect of others and freedom of speech.”⁽⁸²⁾

It tackles all the 20 Competences defined in the Reference Framework of Competences for Democratic Culture (RFCDC). This very important Framework also underlines how relevant it is to embed democratic culture in school governance and to involve students actively in decision-making processes. ⁽⁸³⁾

Moreover, as for the UNITA experience with the process, the use of a secure and certified e-voting platform for the election of student representatives, trains the values and Competences described in the RFCDC guidance for Digital Citizenship.⁽⁸⁴⁾

It fits in the core of the EntreComp Framework, that defines entrepreneurship as: “The capacity to act upon opportunities and ideas to create social, cultural, or financial value for others” and it boosts all the 15 Competences listed.⁽⁸⁵⁾

It resonates with the nine competences relevant for the LifeComp Framework, guaranteeing skills that are indispensable in any context.⁽⁸⁶⁾

Moreover, student representatives activities allow to practice and integrate all the 8 Key Competences on Life Long Learning.⁽⁸⁷⁾

This Good Practice is a first reliable, replicable, adaptable and modifiable example on how students should be taking part in a democratic selection process to enter fully in the decisional processes of European Universities and overall European Higher Education Institutions.

The next step would be for EUAs and European-level policymakers to adopt clear guidelines for democratic student representation, including standardized mechanisms for elections, rotation, and communicational channels. This formalization would not only validate student voices but also uphold transparency, creating conditions for long-term sustainability and deeper cross-border integration in Higher education. As our case suggests, investing in well-defined, participatory governance models can yield all the significant benefits described

above, ultimately aligning alliance initiatives more closely with the evolving needs and aspirations of the European Union.

Democratic governance models are potentially infinite and each offers value in different contexts; however, they can only be built by respecting fundamental principles, investing in the critical education of community members, and relying on institutional imagination and project autonomy that fosters responsibility among participants.

Constituent processes similar to that of the UNITA Student Assembly can be undertaken by all universities within the Alliance, creating a distributed laboratory of innovative and inclusive governance practices.

In this context, student-led spaces can provide important opportunities for students to experiment with new political identities in relatively safe, supportive, and non-threatening environments.⁽⁸⁸⁾

In conclusion, the implementation of democratically elected student representation models is not merely a bureaucratic requirement or an internal governance improvement. It represents an indispensable strategic investment in the future of European democracy and university institutions, as well as in the success of the European Universities Alliances project itself.

Limits and necessary considerations

This Good Practice seeks to avoid any form of short-sightedness and acknowledges that participation is not a panacea: it can fail when local elites capture the process or when the necessary technical capacity and institutional support are lacking.⁽⁸⁹⁾

The impact of student governance participation is influenced by factors such as the quality of the experience, inclusivity, institutional climate, and individual predispositions: supportive environments and opportunities for meaningful participation are crucial to obtain the positive effects. ^(61,63,66,90–93)

These benefits are most pronounced when student participation is meaningful, supported by institutional culture, and embedded in legal frameworks^(14,27,94,95)

Many challenges to full involvement in governance decisional processes persist and they can often lead to frustration and disengagement among students.^(24,26,27,96,97)

It should nevertheless be emphasised that the principles presented in the preceding pages reinforce one another, and that the application of the process outlined below is considered an excellent starting point. Robust participatory mechanisms enhance accountability, and strong accountability generates continuous improvement-oriented feedback that unquestionably leads to meaningful actions in the long term.

In the next chapters, we will further develop the fundamental characteristics for an inclusive engagement of student representatives in the Alliances decisional processes, describing practical steps and tools for the construction of a fully equipped environment.

The final aim of the actions described is to include student representatives fully in an informed decisional process, while recognising the differentiated responsibilities and expertise of the various actors within the academic community, and promoting participation models that are balanced, proportionate, and coherent with each role.

SKILLS, VALUES AND KNOWLEDGE DEVELOPED

Documented benefits of student involvement with voting rights and decision-making power include: (14,23–25,26,27,29,33,73,94,95,98,99)

1. the enhancement of educational quality,
2. increased student satisfaction and stronger sense of belonging to the institution,
3. strengthening of institutional legitimacy and accountability
4. improvements in educational quality assurance,
5. improvements in curriculum development and institutional effectiveness,
6. more responsive and relevant educational programs.

Active participation in governance bodies fosters democratic values, leadership skills, and civic engagement among students. It provides practical experience in: (30,32,33,67,69–71,99,100)

1. Teamwork and Cooperation,
2. Conflict resolution,
3. Critical thinking and problem-solving,
4. Negotiation,
5. Constructive debate and Intercultural communication,
6. Financial and resource management,
7. Autonomous learning and Learning through experience,
8. Management of uncertainty, ambiguity, and risk,
9. Self-regulation and Adaptability in complex systems,

This Good Practice develops, for every actor involved and at different depths, the following RF CDC Values:(83)

1. Human dignity and human rights
2. Democracy
3. Justice
4. Fairness
5. Equality
6. Rule of law
7. Respect for diversity and pluralism
8. Non-discrimination
9. Social responsibility and Collective responsibility for the public good
10. Institutional accountability and respect for democratic legitimacy
11. Transparency in governance
12. Ethical integrity
13. Commitment to inclusive participation and confidence in democratic action

The students involved in the application of the Good Practice and in decisional processes of any institutional board, will develop knowledge about:

1. Democratic principles and processes
2. Electoral systems and procedures

3. Legitimacy and accountability mechanisms
4. Decision-making chains and institutional mandates
5. Internal quality assurance systems
6. Financial governance and budgetary oversight
7. Ethical standards in public roles
8. Conflict of interest management
9. Transnational cooperation
10. Self-awareness as a democratic actor, and impact of individual decisions on collective outcomes
11. University governance structures
12. European Universities Alliances governance

THE UNITA EXPERIENCE

This Good Practice is grounded in a concrete experience developed within the UNITA Alliance.

Student representatives in UNITA

Since its foundation, the Alliance recognised the value of including students in the development of the new European institution and designed its decision-making processes to include student representatives in all Alliance bodies: the Governance Board, the Quality and Evaluation Board, the Management Committee, the Ethical Committee and all Task Teams.

Student representatives hold a minority share of the available seats within these bodies and enjoy the same rights of participation, intervention, voting, and administrative support as all other members.

The role of the Student Assembly in UNITA

From the very beginning, the structure of the UNITA Alliance also envisaged the Student Assembly: a body composed exclusively of student representatives, independent and autonomous, serving as the highest student representative body within the Alliance.

It is the primary forum for student debate within the community and is entrusted, among other responsibilities, with appointing student members to the other Boards of the Alliance. Members who join the Alliance's decision-making bodies are appointed by and from within the Student Assembly, enabling student representatives to coordinate their work and maintain the continuity necessary for coherent and cross-cutting planning.

Any student enrolled at one of the Alliance universities may become a member of the Student Assembly, provided that they stand for election on a representative list (created either independently or collectively by students and composed exclusively of students) and secure a seat in the official elections held every two years.

These elections are open to all students enrolled at each of the Alliance universities.

Starting from the Student Assembly, elected student representatives are involved in every decision of the Alliance by appointing the student members who vote on strategic directives within the Governance Board alongside the Rectors of the universities, define quality assurance criteria and processes within the Quality and Evaluation Board, and shape the operational implementation of decisions within the Legal Entity, the Management Committee, the Ethical Committee and each Task Team of the Alliance.

The whole Alliance student community elects peers as members of the Student Assembly, then the Student Assembly nominates the representatives that will take seats in the other Boards of the Alliance, from between its elected members.

The Constituent process that created the Student Assembly

The constituent process that defined the role of the Student Assembly and its methods, is the result of a spontaneous initiative undertaken by UNITA students who took part in the first Student Assembly meeting ever organised.

It's the core of this Good Practice and a fundamental part of its value.

The Student Assembly held its Kick-Off Meeting immediately following the formal establishment of the Alliance and was required to address three fundamental dilemmas:

- how to organise its internal processes in order to ensure inclusive, comprehensive, structured, and effective debates capable of producing context-appropriate and informed decisions;
- how to integrate the functions of the Student Assembly with the functioning of the Alliance and its member universities;
- what type of process to establish for the turnover of Student Assembly members, who are naturally expected to graduate and therefore step down from their roles after a limited number of years.

In order to respond to these three questions, the students relied on the reflections outlined in the first chapter of this Good Practice and concluded that the only viable solution was to draft, finalize and then approve:

- the Internal Functioning Regulation of the body, describing all internal processes and its relationships with the other bodies of the Alliance and its member universities;
- the Electoral Regulations, outlining the democratic process through which members are selected by the Alliance's student community.

To this end, the Student Assembly was developed as a *Constituent Body* and established that any student regularly enrolled at a member university could become a member of the body and participate in the drafting of the regulations.

The *Constituent* Student Assembly began its work by drawing on the robust guidance provided by research and international literature on the construction of democratic and inclusive processes.

It then analysed the specific characteristics of the universities within the Alliance, taking inspiration from existing procedures, and selecting and integrating the most effective and context-appropriate practices.

The *Constituent* Student Assembly coordinated its work autonomously, requesting input and consultation from professors, experts, other governing bodies, and institutional offices whenever deemed necessary or useful.

All members (any student regularly enrolled at any of the Alliance universities that asked to participate in the Student Assembly meetings and on-going work) voted on every stage, every article, and every process following in-depth debate.

Over time and for different periods, more than 200 individuals including students, academics, and professionals, participated throughout the process. Final decisions were nevertheless discussed, voted upon, and adopted exclusively by the student representatives who were members of the Constituent Assembly.

Once both sets of regulations had been completed, the first official elections of UNITA student representatives were organised through the institutional and administrative structures of the Alliance and its partner universities. This process was carried out in close coordination with the Constituent Student Assembly, which supported and supervised the correct and consistent application of the adopted regulations across the Alliance.

With the end of the electoral process, the Constituent Student Assembly formally fulfilled and concluded its mandate in March 2025. The formal election of the Board members marked the beginning of the first official mandate of the fully constituted Student Assembly.

In the future, elections will be organised every two years by the institutional and administrative structures of UNITA, as part of their ordinary institutional procedures.

The objective of this Good Practice is to enable other University Alliances and Higher Education Institutions to develop their own regulatory frameworks through a student-led constituent process similar to the one described above. The following chapters therefore focus on providing the information necessary to implement the *constituent* activities and to achieve a process that is self-sustaining, democratic, effective, and fully integrated into institutional decision-making processes.

The regulations are attached below and any updates or subsequent amendments are available at: https://univ-unita.eu/Sites/unita/en/Pagina/student_assembly

THE PRACTICE AND HOW TO IMPLEMENT IT

The path followed

The strategic and procedural process for introducing and approving of the regulations was structured as a logical sequence of steps, designed to build consensus and to ensure that the adoption of the regulations would be an orderly, credible, and value-generating process.

1. The first step of the *Constituent* Student Assembly was to recognize its role as a temporary board with a specific mandate, which would end its role as soon as the regulations were finalized, the results of the first elections published and the newly elected Student Assembly convened under the adopted regulations.
2. The *Constituent* Student Assembly then nominated a coordinator of the constituent process, who acted as a moderator during debates and as first responsible actor for the collaboration with other Bodies, members of the Alliance and professionals. More details are described in the following chapters.
3. The discussions started from the definition of the principles and objectives of the constituent process and its outputs. These principles are now summarised in the first articles of the Internal Regulation (linked below).
4. Subsequently, the project was presented to strategic bodies such as the UNITA Quality Evaluation Board, in order to obtain an initial technical, institutional, and meaningful exchange.
5. A sequential approval strategy was adopted. The drafting of the Internal Regulation was addressed first. Every detail of the regulation was discussed and approved by the students within the Student Assembly.
6. To strengthen each step, ensure coherence, align the process with the defined objectives, and adapt it to the specific context, the Student Assembly presented and discussed several elements with:
 - professors from the Alliance universities, covering a wide range of disciplines relevant to the process;
 - university governing bodies and technical offices;
 - external university quality evaluation and assurance bodies.
7. Once the first draft of the Internal Regulation was completed, a formal review of the document was requested from both the Alliance Governance Board and the Quality Evaluation Board. Both bodies were explicitly asked to provide any comments or requests. These were then submitted to the Student Assembly for analysis, and the constituent body decided to accept or reject each of them. A first final version of the Regulation has then been approved. Further details on this phase of the process can be found in the final articles of the Internal Regulation included (linked below).
8. The same process, from step 3 to step 7 of this list, was then repeated for the Electoral Regulation, as a logical and necessary consequence of the first regulation

already approved. Indeed, the Internal Regulation establishes the key principle that the Assembly is composed of elected representatives.

During the drafting of this second regulation, it was at times necessary to introduce amendments to the Internal Regulation as well, as the two regulatory frameworks are clearly interdependent.

9. In parallel with the development and formal approval of both regulations, the resources required for their implementation were mapped and planned, with particular attention to the electoral process. In the case of UNITA, the use of an online voting platform has been foreseen and designed, ensuring minimal costs and the widest possible outreach, while preserving the security and privacy of the process. Technical and financial aspects were addressed through a pragmatic approach, clearly recognising that the limited costs involved represented a significant strategic investment.
10. Following the approval of the regulations and the implementation of the tools required for the elections, the Student Assembly, together with the relevant Alliance offices, developed an institutional communication campaign aimed at encouraging student participation in the elections, both as candidates and as voters.

From a transferability perspective, the key implementation features are: a clear sequencing of steps, formal institutional recognition combined with student autonomy, iterative consultation without loss of democratic control, early planning of technical and communication aspects, and the explicit closure of the constituent phase through elections. These elements can be adapted by other alliances regardless of size, legal framework, or institutional culture, while preserving the core democratic logic of the practice

The implementation of the Good Practice has produced clear, measurable, and structural results within the UNITA Alliance, confirming that the objectives set at the outset have been fully achieved.

Further insight on the outcomes of the process is provided in the section dedicated to KPIs.

The steps of the Constituent Process

The Constituent Student Assembly has met at least once a month online, for the whole period from the Kick-Off Meeting to the first UNITA Student Assembly Elections.

The chronostory of the process below provides a detailed view of the process, but it is important to underline that other Higher Education Institutions will surely find a faster pace in their path, since there is already a working reference to start from.

Consortium Agreement

April 2021

The UNITA Consortium Agreement was signed by all the Universities of the Alliance. It defined the Student Assembly as follows:

“

The Students' Assembly (SA) is one specific participative body, giving an important role to the Students.

The Students' Assembly:

- Is informed of UNITA implementation and decisions
- Is regularly invited to make remarks and proposals
- Is invited to join board meetings and to be a member of decisional and consultative ones with voting rights
- Reports to the students.

Meetings of the Student Assembly are held at least once a month.

“

Student Assembly (SA) Introductory Meeting

January 2021

The first-ever meeting of the SA was introductory, and participants briefly described themselves and their universities.

SA KICK OFF Meeting

May 2021

The members of the Student Assembly (SA) evaluated the nature of the SA as a constituent board and therefore decided to open the discussion to any student of the Alliance willing to participate in meetings.

No restrictions to this participation has been set, except one: if the Agenda of a next meeting was already published, students asking to participate in the decisional process could have entered the Assembly only at the subsequent one.

This restriction was meant to secure a more fair decisional process and voting session for sensible decisions taken over a long period of time and multiple meetings: groups of people willing to impose their view can't add many members from time-to-time to win at voting sessions.

The *Constituent* Student Assembly elected and appointed a president and decided that any decision would have been taken by a relative majority.

Since the first meeting, the Student Assembly has collected Minutes, shared them with all the members and approved them with edits on the subsequent session.

First Year Report November 2021

Research and data collection May 2021

The members of the SA started searching for official documents describing decisional processes in their Universities and in other higher education institutions or existing EUAs. This phase included analysis of meeting notes and official regulations from UNITA institutions, as well as informal interviews with student representatives from different countries and universities of the Alliance.

Documents on the theory of democratic processes and research papers related to on-going processes that could have shaped structure and decisions have been collected too. The collection of these documents has been shared with the whole Student Assembly. A set of links to drafts and useful documents have been shared permanently with the Minutes of the meeting.

First Draft of the Internal Functioning Regulation and ongoing research September 2021

Starting from the documents retrieved from the Universities of the Alliance, a first draft of the Regulation has been created and presented to the Student Assembly, by a commission previously created for the purpose by the Assembly itself.

The research of documents, scientific papers and recognized charts has been going on.

Analysis of more documents and regulations September to December 2021

More documents have been shared about our Universities and an analysis of the regulations available have been made by the members of the Student Assembly, both during the meetings and alone.

First structural decisions on the realization of the Student Assembly Elections 31st May 2022

During one of the first plenary sessions held in presence, core decisions on the realization of elections have been taken: mandate duration (2 years), electoral month (March), electoral mean (digital platform), definition of the electorate (any student properly enrolled in any of the Universities of the Alliance can candidate and vote). The core decisions helped define the necessary actions to take to deliver elections within the shared deadlines.

Nomination of the SA first Governance Board members

April 2022

The members of the Governance Board have been elected between the members of the Student Assembly and by the members of the Student Assembly, based on formal candidatures collected in the previous weeks.

The president of the Student Assembly has been participating in Governance Board meetings before this election, on behalf of the Student Assembly itself.

The SA elects its first Quality & Evaluation Board member

June 2022

Members of the Quality & Evaluation Board have been elected among the members of the Student Assembly and by the members of the Student Assembly, based on formal candidatures collected in the previous weeks.

The president of the Student Assembly has been participating in Governance Board meetings before these elections, on behalf of the Student Assembly itself.

Student Assembly in-presence Meeting

June 2022 - Timișoara (UVT)

The Student Assembly has met regularly in person, at least twice a year, alongside the meetings of the other Boards of the Alliance.

In-person meetings are key because they allow students to:

- get to know each other and bond on a human level, laying the foundation for solid and effective collaboration;
- organize long meetings to address very complex issues in order to make difficult decisions or practically implement some of the more complex steps that require collaborative effort (for example, the implementation of the communications campaign for the upcoming elections).

For logistical and economical reasons, not all members of the Student Assembly can participate simultaneously in in-person meetings, but a delegation from each university has always been present, and all discussions have been made available online for the remaining members.

Apart from actively participating in the Student Assembly meetings and in the other UNITA Boards' meetings (if nominated to them by the Student Assembly), students have the opportunity to meet separately on any deserved occasion, creating committees and working groups for specific tasks.

Presentation of the first draft of the Internal Functioning Regulation to the UNITA

Governance Board and Quality Evaluation Board

June 2022

A first round of recommendations has been collected from the Boards.

Approval of the second draft of the Internal Functioning Regulation after Governance Board and Quality Evaluation Board suggestions.

September 2022

After the collection of the first round of recommendations, all of them have been discussed by the members of the Student Assembly, and some of them have been accepted. A second round of recommendations has then started. Each article of the Regulation was debated and approved by the Student Assembly, while feedback was systematically collected from governance boards, quality assurance bodies, academic experts, and administrative offices. Final decisions always remained with the student representatives, preserving the integrity of the constituent process.

Common Knowledge to build the Electoral Regulation, a first lecture

January 2023

While the discussion on the Electoral Regulation has been going on, the necessity for a common knowledge background grows relevant. Therefore, the Student Assembly has invited Professors to present the most relevant aspects and elements necessary to understand and discuss in a constitutional board.

A Professor from Università di Torino has held a lecture on Electoral Systems, Electoral Methods and Criterias.

First Draft of the Electoral Regulation

January 2023

Starting from the documents retrieved from the Universities of the Alliance, a first draft of the Regulation has been created and presented to the Student Assembly, by a commission previously created for the purpose, by the Assembly itself.

The research of documents, scientific papers and recognized charts has been going on.

Student Assembly in-presence Meeting

February 2023 - Zaragoza (UNIZAR)

Knowledge and application: discussion on the main points of an Electoral regulation

February 2023

During a plenary meeting in-presence, an Associate (?) Professor from Universidad de Zaragoza has held a lecture on Electoral Systems to ensure broader knowledge and a shared starting point for the discussions needed to shape the Electoral Regulation.

During the meeting it was decided that elections will: take place every 2 years, in March, for 2 days long, with open lists, with the Sainte Lague electoral method. A first version of the definition of active electorate (right to stand for elections) and passive electorate (right to vote) has been written. In subsequent meetings, the duration of the voting session has been increased to 3 days: many decisions taken along the way were revised and sometimes changed by the Student Assembly, while adding details and mechanisms to process. Each article and point on the regulation is linked to the others and the whole process required adjustments to maintain consistency and coherency.

First exploratory meeting on E-VOTING

February 2023

A delegation of the Student Assembly nominated during an official meeting, collaborated with TaskTeam 3.4 “Interuniversity Digital Campus” to define the first basic steps to explore the realisation or acquisition of an e-voting platform.

A clear interest of the alliance to pursue through its own means the realisation of a secure e-voting platform has been expressed.

Subsequent meetings on E-VOTING

April 2023

In the subsequent meetings between the Student Assembly and TT3.4 it has been clarified that due to risks of conflict of interests and on the Council of Europe recommendations on e-voting, the Alliance have to find a third-party provider to obtain the e-voting services.

Further drafts on the Electoral Regulation,

April 2023 - July 2024

To draft the Electoral Regulation, questions have been asked to many different Professors experts on the field and Academic offices related to the subject, to have preparatory information useful to the discussion and feedback along the way. This process has been ongoing until the last edit to the final version.

Student Assembly in-presence Meeting

September 2023 - Covilha (UBI)

Student Assembly in-presence Meeting

October 2023 - Chambery (USMB)

First meetings with E-VOTING platform providers

January 2024

Third-party providers for the provision of a secure e-voting platform, must comply with the recommendations of the council of Europe, obtain all the relevant European Certifications and guarantee coercion prevention. The minimum standards described in the Electoral Regulation were shaped parallelly to these meetings and over a long period of time, since most of the necessities are technical and it takes time to fully integrate them into both theory and practice.

A focus should be made on coercion prevention and vote-selling: e-voting platforms are very useful to improve participation in the academic community because they allow the exercise of this right (and duty) from any place in the world through any personal digital device connected to the internet the voter may have at hand. For the same reason, since a voter is not safe inside a private ballot cabin, he/she must be protected with approaches that seem in opposition with traditional physical voting systems.

A protocol is coercion-resistant if voters can cast their ballots as they want, even if someone tries to actively force them to vote for a specific candidate. A protocol is vote-selling resistant if it does not give a proof of vote that can be understood by everyone.

To be coercion-resistant, it must be designed in order to let each voter overwrite her previously submitted ballots, that she may have cast under coercion, such that no-one else including

a possible coercer, can see whether or not the voter has updated her vote.

These two features must be included alongside integrity, anonymity, software independence, eligibility, and verifiability.

Presentation of the E-VOTING platform providers options to TT3.4

April 2024

Attention was given to accessibility, data protection, and coercion-resistant e-voting solutions suitable for a transnational alliance.

First complete revision of the final draft of the Electoral Regulation

May 2024

The revision has taken place with members of the Governance Board, of the Quality & Evaluation Board, of the Management Committee. A deep revision has been made with the office “University Central Collegiate Bodies, Internal Standardisation and Regulatory Compliance Area” at the University of Turin.

Second UNITA Consortium Agreement

June 2024

The new Consortium Agreement for UNITA phase II has been signed and the definition of the Student Assembly has changed to allow the application of the regulations:

“The Student Assembly is self-ruled by the students’ community and has the function of coordinating student representation throughout the Parties and disseminating information on its activities. It nominates 2 representatives per Task Team, 2 in the Governance Board, and 2 in the Quality and Evaluation Board”

Student Assembly in-presence Meeting

June 2024 - Braşov (UNITBV)

Start of the organization of the sensitization campaign on Student Assembly

Elections, to both get students to candidate and vote

June 2024

Governance Board approval for the on e-voting platform acquisition

June 2024

The campaign strategy has been approved for all 3 main actions: physical campaign, digital campaign and involvement of Universities faculty and staff members.

E-voting platform acquisition and integration in the UNITA Virtual Campus

July 2024 - November 2024

First meeting for the integration of the e-voting platform in the UNITA systems, between Student Assembly members, TT3.4 members and provider staff

Governance Board Approval of funding for the communication strategy of the Student Assembly 2025 Election

November 2024

The campaign strategy has been approved for all 3 main actions: physical campaign, digital campaign and involvement of Universities faculty and staff

Last edits on the Electoral Regulation

December 2024

Based on comments from the Governance Board, the Quality Evaluation Board and various universities of the Alliance, some edits to the regulation have been discussed and voted on by the Student Assembly. Some of the requests for amendments could not be accepted because they would have called into question the essential principles underlying the regulations.

All technical comments that contributed to the creation of an efficient and transparent procedure were accepted.

Some comments and questions depended on the difficulty of interpreting the regulations: the structure was optimised to make them as easy to understand as possible.

Privacy Agreement to share necessary data with the platform provider

January 2025

Announcement of the Elections from the Lead Rector of UNITA

January 2025

Student Assembly in-presence Meeting

February 2025 - Pamplona (PNA)

FIRST STUDENT ASSEMBLY ELECTIONS

March 2025

NOMINATION OF THE NEW STUDENT ASSEMBLY MEMBERS by the UNITA Offices and FORMAL CONCLUSION OF THE CONSTITUENT ASSEMBLY MANDATE

April 2025

CONVOCAION OF THE FIRST ASSEMBLY OF THE NEW MANDATE, AND INTERNAL ELECTIONS FOR THE NEW STUDENT ASSEMBLY PRESIDENCY OFFICE

June 2025

FUNDAMENTAL ELEMENTS OF THE PRACTICE OUTPUT

The UNITA Student Assembly has based the identification of indispensable characteristics for a democratic environment on different international accredited documents, available online:

- OSCE/ODIHR Election Observation Handbook (6th ed.)⁽¹⁰¹⁾
<https://www.osce.org/sites/default/files/f/documents/5/e/68439.pdf>
- European Commission For Democracy Through Law (Venice Commission), Code Of Good Practice In Electoral Matters, Guidelines And Explanatory Report, 2002⁽¹⁰²⁾
[www.venice.coe.int/webforms/documents/default.aspx?pdffile=CDL-STD\(2003\)034-e](http://www.venice.coe.int/webforms/documents/default.aspx?pdffile=CDL-STD(2003)034-e)
- Council of Europe, “Recommendation CM/Rec(2017)51 of the Committee of Ministers to member States on standards for e-voting” 2017 ⁽¹⁰³⁾
<https://rm.coe.int/0900001680726f6f>
- IDEA - International Institute for Democracy and Electoral Assistance, “International Obligations for Elections, Guidelines for Legal Frameworks”⁽¹⁰⁴⁾
<https://www.idea.int/publications/catalogue/international-obligations-elections-guidelines-legal-frameworks>
- Council of Europe, “Setting minimum standards for electoral systems in order to offer the basis for free and fair elections”⁽¹⁰⁵⁾ <https://pace.coe.int/en/files/28724/html>
- Inter-Parliamentary Council, Declaration on Criteria for Free and Fair Elections, 1994 ⁽¹⁰⁶⁾
<https://www.ipu.org/impact/democracy-and-strong-parliaments/ipu-standards/declaration-criteria-free-and-fair-elections>
- National Democracy Institute, “Promoting legal frameworks for democratic elections: an NDI guide for developing election laws and law commentaries”⁽¹⁰⁷⁾
<https://www.ndi.org/sites/default/files/Legal%20Frameworks%20Guide%20Sections%201-3%20-%20EN.pdf>
- The Democracy Matrix, 2020.⁽¹⁰⁸⁾ <https://www.democracymatrix.com/conception>.
- The questionnaire used for the EUI Democracy Index Model ⁽¹⁰⁹⁾
www.eiu.com/n/global-themes/democracy-index/

The core elements of a functioning Student Assembly

The following list of criteria is a compendium of what the Student Assembly has found to be necessary for the institutional characteristics of the Board, but is not meant to be exhaustive or reductive on any item that other Alliances may find useful.

Criteria to be part of the *Constituent* Student Assembly

The members of the *Constituent* Student Assembly evaluated the nature of the SA as a constituent board and therefore decided to open the discussion to any student of the Alliance willing to participate in meetings.

No restrictions to this participation has been set, except one: if the Agenda of a next meeting was already published, students asking to participate in the decisional process could have entered the Assembly only at the subsequent one.

This restriction is meant to secure a more fair decisional process and voting session for sensible decisions taken over a long period of time and multiple meetings: groups of people willing to impose their view can't add many members to the voting session to win.

Fundamental Values Recognition

- **Commitment to European Democratic Values:** A Student Assembly should explicitly base its work on the rejection of all forms of discrimination.
- **Principle of Universal Representation:** A Student Assembly is constituted to represent *all* students and PhDs enrolled in the partner universities, ensuring no student category is excluded.
- **Defense of Student Rights:** A Student Assembly core objective is the active defense of student rights and cooperation with local student representative bodies.

Structural Elements for Integration and Autonomy

The model establishes the Student Assembly (SA) of any Alliance as an autonomous body with formally recognized power, moving beyond a purely consultative role.

- **Formalized Role in Governance, at every Board:** The SA holds tangible and balanced power that assigns rights and duties to the council and its members. The recognition of this formalized role comes through:
 - **Nomination authority:** it nominates student representatives directly into any decision-making body: the highest levels of governance, the quality assurance bodies, the teams developing final projects. These nominated student representatives are selected:
 - within the members of the Student Assembly
 - by the members of the Student Assembly
 - **Full voting rights:** the student representatives nominated in each board, have voting rights that are equal in values to the other members of the board. The number of seats reserved for student representatives may represent a minority when compared to the whole board, but it's anyway relevant in proportion to the other stakeholders groups.
 - **Mandatory Consultation Rights,** with formal "mandatory opinion" rights on key annual reports from the Alliance's management and quality boards
 - **Right of Initiative,** allowing it to submit proposals to any Board of the Alliance and of any member University.
 - **Guaranteed Financial and Regulatory Autonomy:** The SA possesses critical levers of self-governance: it creates its own regulations and approves its own annual budget to determine the allocation of its resources.
- **Direct embedding of Students in Operations:** Representation is integrated at the operational level. The SA must nominate at least two of its members to each of the Alliance's "Task Teams" (which are managed by WorkPackages).
- **Hybrid Representation Model:** The SA's composition bridges local and alliance-level governance. Each university holds 8 seats for representatives in the

SA: 7 are elected directly by the student body , and 1 is nominated by the university's local Student Council (or equivalent highest student body). This ensures a permanent, structural link between the central role of the SA and the local student governance structures.

- **Internal Specialization and adaptability:** The SA creates Permanent Commissions (e.g., Education, Student Services, Transparency, PhDs) and Temporary Commissions to develop expertise and manage its workload effectively.

Procedural Elements for Functioning and Transparency

The regulations ensure that day-by-day operations are democratic, transparent, and accessible to all students.

- **Public Transparency as Default:** Meetings are open to any member of the University as auditors. A clear distinction is made between elected members, eventual substitutes, observers, and contributors, with clearly defined rights and responsibilities;
- **Mandatory Accessibility:** All assemblies *must* be made available via streaming to all students of the Alliance. Members are also guaranteed the right to participate remotely and criterias for proper advanced notice on any Meeting or Action are clearly established.
- **Accountability through Public Records and Comprehensive Minutes:** Detailed minutes are mandatory and, after approval, must be published on the Alliance website , ensuring a public record of discussions, decisions, and votes (including abstentions and "against" votes).
- **Financial Transparency:** The SA's budget is public and subject to a mandatory annual examination by the full assembly.
- **Structured Executive Branch and Impeachment processes:** A "Presidency Office" (President, VPs, Secretary, Treasurer, Communication Officers) provides clear leadership and division of labor. The President and the Presidency office are in charge of the coordination of the Student Assembly activities and work as moderators. If the majority of the Assembly finds the elected composition of its Presidency Office to be inadequate for the role, an impeachment procedure can be applied and new elections of the presidency will be held.
- **Principle of Diverse Leadership:** The President and Vice-Presidents must be elected in the Presidency Office from different universities, to prevent any domination by a single institution.
- **Institutional Continuity between mandates and Institutional memory:** A detailed "transition folder" and handover process is mandated to ensure a seamless transfer of knowledge, records, and ongoing projects between outgoing and incoming Presidency Offices.
- **Regular cadence, frequent and participated meeting schedule:** at least 1 ordinary meeting a month is guaranteed and any member can call for extraordinary sessions, through a clearly defined process.
- **Member statement rights and Attendance obligations:** both rights and duties of the members of the Student Assembly are clearly stated, taking into account actions both for any right not fulfilled and for any duty not expressed.

- **Consistency between nominations and actual participation in Alliance bodies:** Accountability measures and impeachment procedures are established to ensure responsibility and continuity.
- **Replacement of Members and anti-vacancy provisions:** the succession in case of graduation or anyway dismissal of a member, is clearly defined. New elections are held in case no replacement of a seat is available. establishment of clear substitution procedures, consistent with electoral regulations and internal rules, to ensure uninterrupted representation;
- **Bottom-Up Agenda Setting:** Any member of the Student Assembly can request late additions to the Agenda. Any student can add a point to the SA agenda, through a proposal signed by a minimum number of peers: the SA is then obliged to discuss the point and the signatories can select one student to present the proposal at the meeting.
- **Stakeholder consultation and Reporting obligations:** Representatives nominated from the Assembly in other Boards or for external bodies and projects, must report back to the Assembly itself, ensuring continuity and knowledge-based discussions
- **Quorum requirements** for any decisional process are clearly defined.

Principles of Electoral Integrity

The electoral regulation establishes a comprehensive, fair, and transparent process to electing representatives, managed with professional oversight.

- **Principle of Proportional Representation:** The election uses a competing list system with proportional representation. This is a crucial democratic choice to ensure that minority lists and viewpoints can gain representation, rather than a "winner-take-all" system.
- **Candidature opportunities open to all students:** Any candidate must be part of a list: can either create one or enter in one. New lists need 50 non-candidate signatures per university, to enter the competition. The signatures are a tool to demonstrate that the candidates exist and are part of the community: those who sign for the list to candidate, should not necessarily be future voters of the list and its candidates (signatures from oppositors are actually an indicator of a healthy debate).
- **Multi-Level Independent Oversight:** The Electoral Commissions are multi-stakeholder bodies (faculty, students, administrators) that share the responsibility to verify electoral integrity: the process is not self-managed by students alone, to fully prevent conflict of interests while recognizing the relevance of these processes. It should be established at least as a two-tiered oversight structure:
 - **Local Electoral Commissions:** One in *each* university, composed of diverse stakeholders including the Rector (or delegates), Professors, administrative staff, and students.
 - **General Commission:** An alliance-level body composed of members from each local commission, tasked with ensuring equal treatment and acting as the final body for appeals.
- **Accessible and Secure Voting:**
 - **Maximized Access:** Voting is held over a set number of consecutive days to accommodate all schedules.

- Hybrid Access: It primarily uses a secure e-voting platform but also requires physical polling stations at each university for students without personal devices available.
- **Non-exclusion and continuity of political rights, even in digital settings:** The right to vote should be automatic, universal, and continuous for all eligible students. In e-voting contexts, privacy or data-protection interpretations must not introduce an opt-in mechanism that functions as a de-facto disenfranchisement tool. Requiring students to explicitly authorize inclusion in an e-voting system months before an election transforms a fundamental democratic right into a conditional opportunity. In practice, this undermines accessibility, equal suffrage, and informed participation. Automatic inclusion of all eligible students at the time of voting is therefore a necessary safeguard to ensure equal access, effective participation, and the integrity of democratic representation within the Alliance.
- **Digital e-Voting Platform:** Given the size of an alliance and the geographic distances that can generate significant logistical difficulties, online voting platforms are the most practical, cost-effective, and easy-to-manage and integrate tool for an alliance that must organize transnational elections that meet all criteria for privacy, security, secrecy of the vote, and reliability of results. It is necessary to use a third-party platform, rather than producing one internally, to avoid internal conflicts of interest and ensure the highest standards of security and technical updates. A crucial feature required by the process in the case of UNITA is the ability to prevent coercion: modern e-voting systems allow voters to express their preferences from their personal device, in public, without undermining their right to freedom of choice and the secrecy of the vote.
 With coercion prevention systems, a voter has the right to log back in and change his vote at any time during the election period without limits, while protecting the data that links the voter and his preferences. The final vote casted is the only one that counts and therefore the system makes any attempt at coercion ineffective.
- **Public Scrutiny:** The counting of votes is held publicly and can be attended in person or online. This helps demonstrate the institutional recognition of the value of the process, while guaranteeing transparency.
- **Regulated Campaigning and Sanctions:** "Electoral propaganda" is clearly defined and the regulations guarantee fair access for campaigning (e.g., in classrooms) to any candidate list, and establish a "silent period" before the vote. Clear sanctions for violations, including the annulment of votes or suspension of the right to hold office, are described.
- **Clear Succession Rules:** The system ensures democratic continuity. If a representative resigns, they are replaced by the next candidate on their same list. This respects the proportional outcome of the election.

PREREQUISITES

Barriers and Solutions on the involvement of students in decision-making roles in the governance of higher education institutions

Effective implementation of the Good Practice requires political will and top-down legitimacy. It is essential to obtain the explicit commitment of the highest governance bodies: policymakers must recognize student participation as a strategic investment.

Furthermore, the need for a hybrid and formalized governance structure must be clear: the representation model must combine democratic legitimacy and institutional links, ensuring that the elected Student Assembly has formal power (voting rights and mandatory input) as well as a quota of financial autonomy.

Student participation is a multilevel phenomenon involving personal, institutional, and sociopolitical dimensions. Action is required within each level.⁽¹¹⁰⁾

Items for the whole Institution

1. Institutional Mandate and Equal Governance Rights

Student representatives must be fully recognised as legitimate governance actors, and therefore, must enjoy the same rights and duties as all other members of the Alliance's governance Boards, including full voting rights, access to information, and participation in deliberative processes.

Implementation elements

This requires:

- formal recognition of student representatives within the Alliance's governance framework and statutes;
- equal access to all governance-related information, including agendas, background documents, strategic plans, and minutes;
- provision of the same digital tools used by other Board members, such as Alliance platforms, shared document repositories, intranet access, and internal communication channels;
- dedicated administrative and logistical support for meeting preparation, documentation, coordination, and follow-up activities;
- mutual availability and commitment of all Board members to ensure timely interaction and effective collaboration

Indicators

- Formal inclusion of student representatives in governance regulations
- Equal access credentials granted within a defined timeframe after election
- Inclusion in all official Board communications and document repositories

2. Structured Electoral Framework and Institutional Commitment

The election of student representatives must be conducted through a clear, public, and regulated framework, formally endorsed and actively supported by the Alliance and its member institutions.

Implementation elements

- clear institutional commitment to support the process through professional expertise, administrative assistance, and adequate funding;
- involvement of institutional offices and academic staff to ensure procedural robustness, neutrality, and continuity of representation;
- regular and predictable renewal cycles to maintain democratic legitimacy.

Indicators

- Publicly available electoral regulation and timeline
- Formal institutional endorsement and allocation of resources
- Documented election results and mandate durations

3. Defined Oversight Roles and Counterbalances

Electoral integrity and trust require independent oversight and clear separation of responsibilities.

Electoral commissions must be composed of quotas of different academic stakeholders, to ensure that counterbalances compensate for any possible conflict of interests: these roles and proportions are key to supervise the electoral process, ensure compliance with regulations, and address disputes.

Implementation elements

- clearly defined mandates for local and Alliance-level electoral commissions;
- pluralistic composition including different actors of the academic community;
- transparent procedures for verifying candidacies, supervising voting operations, and handling appeals;
- documented escalation mechanisms for resolving disputes.

Indicators

- Formal inclusion of student representatives in governance regulations
- Composition and mandates of commissions publicly available
- Records of decisions and appeals
- Defined timelines for dispute resolution

4. Accessibility Through Secure E-Voting and Data Protection Compliance

Broad participation across countries, institutions, and time zones requires accessible voting mechanisms that guarantee fairness, privacy, and trust.

Elections must be conducted using secure e-voting systems that maximise participation while fully complying with European data protection standards.

Implementation elements

- full compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), including:
 - clear definition of data controller and processor roles;
 - data processing agreement (DPA) with the provider;
 - completion of a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA);
 - defined data retention and deletion policies.

Indicators

- Signed DPA and completed DPIA
- Public documentation of voting procedures and safeguards
- Verified audit or technical compliance documentation

5. In-Person Governance Cycle and Hybrid Participation

The Student Assembly must be guaranteed regular in-person meetings aligned with the governance cycle of the Alliance. Effective governance requires collaboration, in-depth analysis and deliberation, collective decision-making, and time that are not possible to reach only through online meetings.

Those meetings should be organized alongside the other in-presence Alliance Boards meetings that are normally scheduled throughout the year to build stronger networks and boost achievements.

For logistical and budget-related reasons, not all the members of the Student Assembly can participate simultaneously in in-presence meetings, but a delegation from each University has always been present and all the discussions have been made available online for the remaining members.

Implementation elements

- at least two in-person plenary meetings per year, organised alongside meetings of other Alliance Boards where possible;
- financial and logistical arrangements to ensure fair representation of all partner universities;
- hybrid participation mechanisms guaranteeing full speaking and voting rights for members unable to attend in person;
- systematic recording and online publication of discussions and decisions to ensure transparency and inclusiveness.

Indicators

- Number of in-person meetings held annually
- Representation of member universities at meetings
- Availability of recordings and minutes within defined deadlines

6. Institutional Communication and Accountability to the Student Community

Democratic representation requires continuous accountability and transparent communication with the student electorate.

The Student Assembly must be recognised as an official point of reference for the student community and be provided with institutional communication channels.

Implementation elements

- establishment of an official Student Assembly email address and communication identity;
- regular publication of newsletters or reports informing students about activities, decisions, and future initiatives;
- active and accessible communication channels, including social media, managed in coordination with institutional communication offices;
- clear response and feedback mechanisms for student inquiries and concerns.

Indicators

- Frequency of newsletters or reports
- Accessibility and multilingual availability of communication materials

7. Capacity Building, Continuity, and Recognition of Student Representatives

Student representation is inherently time-limited; continuity, effectiveness, and inclusiveness depend on structured support and recognition.

Institutions must ensure systematic onboarding, training, and recognition of student representatives.

Implementation elements

- structured onboarding processes, including knowledge transfer between outgoing and incoming representatives;
- development of onboarding materials outlining responsibilities, ongoing projects, and governance procedures;
- dedicated training activities on governance, leadership, intercultural communication, ethics, and inclusion;
- formal recognition of student representatives' contributions through certificates, micro-credentials, or comparable mechanisms;
- reasonable academic flexibility and non-retaliation safeguards to allow representatives to fulfil their mandate without negative academic consequences;
- allocation of operational resources to support Student Assembly activities, with discretionary budgets considered as a recommended enhancement.

Indicators

- Existence of onboarding materials and handover processes
- Number of training activities delivered
- Formal recognition mechanisms adopted
- Policies on academic flexibility and protection from retaliation

8. Engagement, Inclusiveness, and Risk Mitigation

Even robust governance frameworks may face challenges related to participation and representativeness.

Active measures must be taken to engage the student body and mitigate risks to democratic legitimacy.

Implementation elements

- institutional and student-led awareness campaigns to promote participation and explain the value of student representation;
- targeted outreach to underrepresented groups to foster equitable participation;
- continuous monitoring of voter turnout, representation gaps and engagement levels;
- periodic evaluation and adjustment of procedures based on feedback and evidence.

Indicators

- Voter turnout data and trend analysis
- Diversity metrics among elected representatives
- Documented evaluation and improvement actions

9. Academic Flexibility and Institutional Safeguards for Student Representatives

Student representatives exercising formal governance responsibilities within a European University Alliance must be able to perform their mandate without being disadvantaged in their academic trajectory or exposed to conflicts of interest. Effective student participation requires institutional safeguards that recognise governance duties as a legitimate component of academic life.

Higher Education Institutions should formally guarantee reasonable academic flexibility for elected student representatives in order to accommodate their governance responsibilities, while fully preserving academic standards, assessment criteria and learning outcomes.

Implementation elements

Institutions should adopt clear and transparent measures that may include:

- justified flexibility in academic scheduling;
- recognition of justified absences from classes or academic activities linked to participation in officially mandated meetings of the Student Assembly or Alliance Boards;
- explicit protection against academic retaliation or undue pressure arising from the exercise of representative functions;
- clarification that academic evaluation remains independent and objective, and that governance roles neither grant academic advantages nor expose students to disadvantages.

Student representatives, while remaining fully accountable to their electorate and to the Student Assembly's internal rules, should not be subject to hierarchical dependency or informal pressure from academic authorities in relation to their governance role. Institutional

frameworks should clearly separate academic supervision from governance participation to avoid conflicts of interest.

Indicators

- Existence of a formal policy or institutional guidelines on academic flexibility for student representatives
- Documented procedures for justified absences and rescheduling
- Evidence of non-retaliation safeguards and grievance mechanisms
- Positive feedback from student representatives regarding the balance between academic and governance responsibilities

Items for the Student Assembly

This item refers most all to the *Constituent* process, as a moment with unclear and yet-to-define structured processes, as well as a launching period that should put the basis of present and future integration in the Alliance processes.

All these items are useful also when the Assembly is fully formed, and most of them should be described precisely in the Regulations produced.

1. Predictable Governance Calendar and Effective Internal Coordination

Rationale

Student Assemblies operating at the alliance level involve a large number of representatives distributed across institutions, countries, and academic calendars. Without predictable and coordinated scheduling mechanisms, participation risks becoming uneven, decision-making inefficient, and internal governance weakened. Ensuring effective time management and coordination is therefore a prerequisite for sustainable internal functioning.

Minimum standard

The Student Assembly must operate on the basis of a shared, predictable, and formally approved governance calendar, established sufficiently in advance to allow all members to organise their academic and personal commitments.

Implementation elements

- adoption of structured scheduling tools (e.g. polls or digital planning platforms) to identify timeframes compatible with the largest possible number of members;
- approval of a periodical calendar (6-months to 1 year long) of ordinary meetings at the beginning of each governance year; this also helps distinguishing clearly between ordinary and extraordinary sessions;
- standards for advanced publication of meeting dates, agendas, and expected workloads to enable informed planning;
- alignment, where possible, of Student Assembly meetings with the broader governance cycle of the Alliance to ensure coherence, continuity and networking opportunities.

2. Continuity, Turnover Management, and Substitution Mechanisms

Rationale

High turnover is an inherent characteristic of student representation, due to graduation, changes in enrolment status, or mobility between institutions. Without formal mechanisms to manage continuity and substitution, Student Assembly activities risk fragmentation, loss of institutional memory, and delays in project implementation.

Minimum standard

Clear and transparent procedures must be in place to manage turnover, ensure continuity of representation, and enable the timely substitution of inactive or outgoing members, while safeguarding democratic legitimacy.

For the constituent process to be in place and continuous, is sufficient to establish that:

- any student enrolled at the university can take part in the on-going work for the production of the regulations and in any other activity of the Constituent Assembly
- if a meeting has already been convened and its Agenda has already been published, students asking to participate in the decisional process can enter the Assembly only at the subsequent one.

This restriction is meant to secure a more fair decisional process and voting session for sensible decisions taken over a long period of time and multiple meetings: groups of people willing to impose their view can't add many members to the voting session to win.

Implementation elements

- maintenance of an updated registry of active members and their mandates;
- encouragement of broad internal communication and peer-to-peer dissemination to maintain engagement and renew participation over time.
- Availability of onboarding materials and handover documentation

3. Accountability, Performance Requirements, and Peer Oversight

Rationale

Effective representation requires not only democratic legitimacy but also active participation and accountability. When Student Assembly members are nominated to represent the Assembly in Alliance bodies or specific projects, failure to fulfil these responsibilities undermines both institutional credibility and the Assembly's capacity to influence decision-making.

Minimum standard

The Student Assembly must establish clear accountability mechanisms to ensure that representatives fulfil the mandates entrusted to them, including peer-based oversight and transparent procedures for replacement in cases of persistent non-performance.

Implementation elements

- formal definition of attendance and participation requirements for members nominated to represent the Student Assembly in external bodies or projects;

- introduction of peer-based mechanisms allowing any member of the Student Assembly to request a review of a representative's mandate in cases of sustained non-participation;
- guarantee of due process, including the right of the concerned member to provide explanations before any decision is taken;
- transparent nomination and substitution procedures to ensure collaboration between members, continuity of representation and institutional trust.

4. Communication Strategy, Decentralized Dissemination Capacity and Stakeholder Engagement

Rationale

In transnational University Alliances, centralized communication and governance structures alone are insufficient to ensure meaningful integration of the Student Assembly within the broader student community. Effective representation and institutional legitimacy depend on the Assembly's ability to disseminate information, engage stakeholders, and foster participation across all partner universities.

Given the diversity of institutional, cultural, and educational contexts involved, any member of the Student Assembly should be held responsible as a powerful contact point, part of a wide network. Decentralized dissemination mechanisms and structured engagement with existing student organisations are essential to embed the Student Assembly within the daily academic and social life of the Alliance.

Minimum standard

The Student Assembly must encourage and develop systematic dissemination of its activities at local level and engagement with student stakeholders (associations, informal groups, etc...) across all partner universities.

Implementation elements

- designation of Student Assembly members as responsible for the communication strategy;
- designation of Student Assembly members as local points of contact or ambassadors within their home universities, responsible for disseminating information and collecting feedback from the student community;
- coordination with existing student associations, councils, and representative bodies at the institutional level, ensuring complementarity and avoiding duplication of roles;
- organisation of outreach activities, presentations, and information sessions—both online and in person—aimed at raising awareness of the Student Assembly's role, activities, and opportunities for participation;
- creation of feedback channels allowing students and student organisations to contribute to proposals, express concerns, and share perspectives on the Student Assembly's work;
- adoption of an adaptive and iterative approach to engagement strategies, recognising that complex and evolving institutional contexts require continuous adjustment and learning;

- documentation and centralisation of dissemination outcomes and stakeholder inputs to inform collective decision-making and strategic planning at Alliance level.

Lessons Learned

There are many different types of representation and each decision on the most little detail has massive consequences on the whole structure, its objectives, its power and the outcomes.

The UNITA Regulations are only one the different ways representation can be designed respecting the fundamental characteristics for a democratic environment.

An example:

The UNITA Student Assembly has decided to apply a distribution of seats inside the Assembly that is not proportionate to the number of students enrolled in each University of the Alliance: every university of the Alliance receives the same number of seats.

This decision has been made despite big differences in Universities dimensions, in order to force an international approach in student representatives willing to obtain the majority at board meetings. A perfectly equal number of seats per each University is a big constraint for lists, that pushes them to find candidates in multiple Universities of the Alliance at the same time.

While minorities should always be represented within an academic community, this distribution of seats inside the Assembly is not at all proportionate to the number of students enrolled in each University of the Alliance. These quotas are an example of what may be changed, to maintain balance while fulfilling other relevant characteristics such as more proportional representation of the community.

IMPACT AND KPIs

The following data have been collected until the production of this Good Practice, in January 2026 and are meant to demonstrate the impact of the Good Practice in terms of governance inclusion, participation, and operational outcomes. Please consider that these results were achieved primarily during the *constituent* process and that the full Student Assembly now has greater capacity and resources to further increase its impact.

Formal inclusion of student representatives in governance processes

- Every Board of the Alliance has student representatives that hold the same rights and duties of the other members:
Governance Board, Quality and Evaluation Board, Management Committee, Ethical Committee and all the Task Teams of the Alliance.
- Overall number of students involved directly in the creation of the Regulations: **127**
- Number of seats for students representatives elected in the Student Assembly: **96, 8 per each University**

Electoral Data

- Number of students who voted at the first round of elections in March 2025: **15.874**
- Overall participation at the first round of elections in March 2025: **8,34%**

Operational Data

- Number of official Student Assembly plenary meetings made yet: **42**
- Number of internal commissions created, to discuss and develop different actions **11**
- Number of in-person meetings held: **6**
- UNITA Student Assembly has expanded its network, joining forces with many different international, national, and local student associations. The Board now plays a relevant role in institutions and organizations dedicated to students and education in Europe:
 - is the first official member of the “ESU (European Students’ Union) Conference of Alliances”

- has members in the Executive Committee of the FOREU4ALL “Student-Led Community” topical group
- has been invited to present its work in several ESU events and at the ESN Erasmus Generation Meeting 2025
- has participated in all 5 editions of the “European Student Assembly”

Actions taken through the years

- number of projects or events organized by the Student Assembly: **4**

- number of institutional projects or events that the Student Assembly members has participated to, on behalf of UNITA and of the Student Assembly (not counting events related to decisional processes): **21**

Contributions to communication and dissemination, by the Student Assembly

- On the Student Assembly social media pages:
 - number of contents produced: **20**
 - average number of users reached, per post: **11.360**

- On the Alliance pages:
 - number of contents produced in collaboration with the Student Assembly: **12**

TESTIMONIALS

“Being a student representative in UNITA who got the opportunity to work on the electoral process, allowed me to care deeply about something bigger than myself and to give my time and voice to others. Even when the work load was a lot, it was a warm and meaningful experience that shaped who I am and how I choose to show up for others.”

- Silva, Beatriz

“This feat shows the commitment and capability of European students and universities to organise democratically beyond national and cultural borders. Which is what Europe stands for”

- Ruiz Calvo, Pablo - Student Assembly member both during the Constituent mandate and the Full Mandate of the Body

“As a student who has been actively involved in the project both before and after the official establishment of the UNITA Students’ Assembly, I believe that the electoral process has had a clearly positive impact. The elections have helped to increase the visibility of the project within the university community and have significantly contributed to fostering greater interest, engagement, and participation among students.”

- Asan-Barut, Inês - Student Assembly member both during the Constituent mandate and the present Full Mandate of the Body

“I believe a good practice is conducting elections through online platforms, as this increases accessibility and allows students, regardless of their campus location, to participate with just one click.”

- Oros, Naomi Adela - Student Assembly member and Management Committee member

“As someone involved in organizing the Student Assembly elections, I consider this experience to be very positive and important for the active participation of student representatives and for consolidating the role of the UNITA. As an international initiative, the preparatory work provided a concrete opportunity for cultural exchange and discussion on the topic of democratic representation: procedures and methods for student involvement were discussed, bringing together diverse experiences and practices, with the common goal of ensuring transparency, accessibility, and fairness in the process. A particularly significant element is that the electoral process was governed from the bottom up, starting with the students themselves: student representatives played a leading role both in drafting the regulations and in the organizational implementation of the elections, directly contributing to the definition of shared and concretely applicable rules. Naturally, in my opinion, some areas for improvement also emerged—for example, strengthening communication and providing greater support to candidates in the initial stages—which will certainly be capitalized in future elections to make the process even more widely known, inclusive, and participatory.”

- Lauria, Massimiliano - Legal Office, University of Turin

“As one of the few students who had the opportunity to work on UNITA since the first meeting in January 2020, I was able to really understand the importance, but also all the difficulties, that such an ambitious project entailed.

Most importantly though, I was able to really appreciate all the effort and ideas put in by the hundreds of actors involved in it, which eventually led to a successful result.

With these good practices, we have the possibility to completely reshape the European academic landscape, and to greatly increase the cohesion of students inside and across national borders.”

- Sangermano, Bartolomeo

ATTACHMENTS

The UNITA Student Assembly Electoral Regulation Internal Function Regulation

that product of this Good Practice, are available at
<https://univ-unita.eu/our-alliance/who-we-are/student-assembly/>

Some of the contents used during the institutional communication campaign on the Student Assembly elections:

POSTERS

STICKERS

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